

Service and Resource Management Enablers for 6G Networks

George Makropoulos

National Centre for Scientific Research Demokritos
Institute of Informatics and Telecommunications
Athens, Greece
Email: gmakropoulos@iit.demokritos.gr

Sándor Laki

Faculty of Informatics
ELTE Eötvös Loránd University
Budapest, Hungary
Email: lakis@inf.elte.hu

Abstract—Next generation networks will contain mechanisms at various levels to optimize the resource allocation needed for improved service management. At the same time, these mechanisms introduce their own set of challenges. Specifically, future 6G networks need enabler technologies to handle an unprecedented number of heterogeneous slices under stringent Service Level Agreements, necessitating advanced zero-touch Management and Orchestration, ensuring cloud-to-edge continuum and the management of heavily dynamic environments like Non-Terrestrial Networks. In this paper, we overview these emerging challenges and show key enablers developed in various SNS JU projects for handling them. By harmonizing these technologies, 6G networks can achieve intelligent, scalable, and sustainable orchestration in diverse and rapidly evolving environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

6G networks are expected to intelligently support a massive number of simultaneous and heterogeneous slices associated with various vertical use cases. In this respect, challenges of scalability and sustainability might surface in the deployment of AI-driven zero-touch Management and Orchestration (MANO) of the End-to-End (E2E) slices, under stringent Service Level Agreements (SLAs).

This work discusses the different enabler technologies developed in various SNS-JU research projects to cover the management challenges of future communication systems. The paper presents various technologies grouped into three main categories: 1) High-level Service Management components including intent-based approaches; 2) Enablers solving the management problems of cloud-to-edge computing continuum; and 3) Technologies supporting the management of resources in dynamically changing environments including Non-Terrestrial (NTN) networks.

II. HIGH-LEVEL SERVICE MANAGEMENT

A cohesive and adaptable service management and orchestration (SMO) framework is emerging as a crucial aspect in future 6G networks. The following subsections provide details on how Open RAN's evolution converges to a Common SMO framework covering all the network domains. They also highlight how intent-driven approaches simplify and streamline SMOs, and examines the possible use of multi-agent systems to enable end-to-end E2E SMO capabilities. These developments collectively underscore the growing need for intelligent adaptive service management in the next generation networks.

A. Open RAN evolution towards a common SMO

From the standpoint of architectural evolution in 5G Open RAN, several key drivers and advancements are emerging, particularly through O-RAN Alliance extensions of 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) towards 6G [1]. One major evolution involves the development of a more integrated, standalone O-RAN 'Common SMO' that unifies the functionalities of both RAN and higher-layer orchestration components. Consequently, these higher-layer orchestration functions—collectively referred to as the SMO in O-RAN—are expected to evolve into a comprehensive "6G Common SMO". In this context, the current non-RT RIC and rApps are being extended across domains to support broader orchestration and intelligence. The programmability and extensibility enabled by the O-RAN Near-Real Time (RT) RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) with xApps have been also instrumental, especially in advancing Beyond 5G (B5G) capabilities like energy efficiency. This cross-domain integration—with exposed Application Programmable Interfaces (APIs) marks a foundational step in the evolution of the 5G SMO toward a 6G-ready architecture.

B. Intent driven architecture

As service complexity of 6G increases, network management faces challenges of performance guarantee and complexity reduction. Network management automation; e.g., zero-touch networks [2] and intent-based networks (IBN) [3], can be part of a solution offering improved efficiency and streamlining the operations. Intent-Based Networking is essential for 6G Network to meet business objectives. As a result, it converts goals and restrictions into executable directives to perform the required operations. This permits more flexible decision-making in network management, allowing systems to automatically choose the best plans. IBN is included in SMO and is the cognitive engine that relates business intents with network infrastructure in 6G. Moreover, it enables the active and flexible management of the network by dynamically adapting to new needs.

C. Multi-agent based E2E SMO

Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) are envisioned for 6G networks to distribute decision-making and knowledge across various network entities [4]. MAS consists of AI-based agents that communicate and share knowledge to solve complex

problems that a single agent cannot solve on its own. In 6G, the network nodes will interact with each other to share data, control information, and models, creating self-organized systems. Decisions will be made by each agent based on real-time information, with AI/ML methods such as reinforcement learning (RL) and long short-term memory (LSTM) being used to provide rapid responsiveness. Agents will also share aggregated data and models with the E2E SMO, which plays a crucial role in managing activities between segments (e.g., RAN, cloud, transport). It supports activities like resource optimization, service reallocation upon failures, and energy minimization. Agent deployment and reconfiguration, as well as the creation and reconfiguration of AI/ML pipelines based on the needs of the network, like rerouting services and migrating agents between different 6G domains, will be managed by the SMO.

III. EDGE-TO-CLOUD CONTINUUM

The increasing demands for low-latency and high-performance computing have driven the emergence of an edge-to-cloud computing continuum architecture. This architecture seamlessly integrates edge and cloud resources to deliver efficient and responsive services. This section explores the critical components and frameworks required to build and manage this continuum, which spans from centralized cloud infrastructures to highly distributed edge resources.

A. Programming models for Edge-Cloud continuum

In the edge-cloud continuum, devices across the edge, fog, and cloud layers vary significantly in terms of compute power, memory capacity, network latency, and energy availability. This heterogeneity creates complexity in application development and deployment. To address this challenge and abstract the underlying infrastructure differences, various programming models have been introduced (e.g., Reprorun [5], split computing framework, COMP Superscalar, oneAPI, federated learning (FL) framework). These programming models and frameworks are employed for the design of application and network workflows that leverage split and distributed computing, advanced learning techniques or intra-node reprogrammability of Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA)-based devices.

B. Integrated edge cloud continuum

The flexible deployment of cloud-native solutions across a heterogeneous edge-to-cloud continuum, combined with multi-tenancy and distributed execution, necessitates a unified design for service orchestration, management, and control. A distributed or hierarchical architecture could be adopted, balancing a global multi-site view with localized edge-site perspectives. This approach [6] enables end-to-end optimization (e.g., service migration, edge federation, mobility support) while also allowing lightweight, localized orchestration for tasks like intra-node optimization and interference management. On top of this, the provision of necessary framework and common interfaces will facilitate the design and the life cycle management (LCM) of AI-powered solutions, towards the handling of the necessary data collection and management of the processes. This architecture defines components that apply to the orchestration of the cloud-native services and computing resources, whereas others form part of the B5G network

orchestration, control and management plane. In respect to the Life Cycle Management (LCM) of cloud-native services and computing resources, the relevant components are summarized below:

- Multi-site Service Orchestrator, with an End-to-End (E2E) scope spanning across the edge-to-cloud compute continuum, formed by multiple edge sites, as well as cloud resources.
- Edge-site Intent-driven Orchestrator, overseeing the LCM of the applications/services and resources on each local edge site or point-of-presence.
- Distributed Workflow Orchestrator, responsible for handling the distributed execution of complex application workflows across the compute continuum.

With respect to the B5G networking system, the key components are:

- Multi-site and Edge-site Intelligent RAN Controllers, responsible for the management of the RAN elements
- Slice Manager, handling the LCM of end-to-end network slices. Network slicing is a critical concept in B5G, enabling the development of several virtualized and separated network instances on a shared physical infrastructure.
- Intra-node Micro-orchestrator for software and accelerated computed resources, enabling the joint micro-orchestration of the radio and computing resources (e.g in FPGA-based SoC accelerators)

C. Integration and orchestration of extreme edge resources

The extended cloud continuum comprises centralized cloud resources, distributed edge resources, and heterogeneous extreme edge resources. The integration and orchestration of these extreme edge resources within the compute continuum require the necessary interfaces and components; however, this integration brings forth a set of new challenges. Towards this direction, specific enablers and approaches can be utilised to tackle the challenges such as Multi-cluster resource management, decentralised orchestration and Orchestration of the extreme edge including ETSI MEC enhancements. Focusing on the last topic, a significant development is the constrained Multi-access Edge Computing (cMEC) [7] which extends the traditional MEC (tMEC) introduces efficient features and a layered design that allows it to function as a complete MEC system when resources permit.

D. Meta Operating systems to support edge cloud continuum

As the available distributed computing domains and the volume of data continues to increase, mechanisms that help make optimal use of the edge-cloud computing continuum at its full extent have become more and more necessary. Building on the “classical” concept of meta-Operating Systems (OS) [8], [9], future framework may consider a Meta-Operating System (meta-OS) as an enabler for managing the underlying edge-cloud computing continuum infrastructure. Focusing on service orchestration, a meta-OS envisions a clear two-level

structured orchestrator, the core network and any software-based supporting service. The meta-OS has to be deployed in the different domains composing the continuum and all the provided services (Federation, Data fabric, Cybersecurity, Trust management, AI decision support and Embedded analytic tools) work together based on a common continuum ontology [10] and can be consumed by the MNOs to enhance other business-related use cases beyond orchestration.

IV. DYNAMIC RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Dynamic Resource and Infrastructure management plays a crucial role in next generation networks due to rapidly fluctuating demands and rising user expectations. This area emphasizes adaptive, intelligent, and decentralized strategies for optimizing resources in real time to address the growing complexity, heterogeneity, and dynamic nature of future communication networks.

A. AI/ML for Resource Management

To minimize the volume of monitoring and telemetry data transmitted to centralized locations and to enhance decision-making efficiency, AI and ML algorithms should ideally be executed close to the data plane. Intent-Based Networking (IBN) facilitates this by establishing local control loops while still maintaining centralized coordination and enabling knowledge sharing [12]. Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques have been explored extensively for near-real-time resource management scenarios [13], [14].

Addressing the increasing complexity inherent in network management, 6G technologies are anticipated to adopt a re-architected transport network control structure, relying significantly on distributed knowledge and decision-making mechanisms enabled by Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) [15]. These systems, employing RL techniques combined with inter-agent communication, will enhance responsiveness and coordination, significantly advancing optical and packet network control capabilities. Local agents can quickly modify the data plane (e.g., redirecting traffic to an alternative path, etc.) to satisfy service requirements or SLAs.

In alignment with this distributed approach, the evolution of the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), as specified in 3GPP TS 23.288 Release-18 [11], emphasizes a shift toward distributed analytics. This involves decentralizing NWDAF responsibilities between central consumer functions and local analytics sources to facilitate flexible telemetry collection, federated learning, and distributed data processing. These developments are foundational to supporting future native AI/ML capabilities in Radio Access Networks (RAN).

To effectively manage the complexity and diversity of network infrastructures, extending the Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework with an AI-based service deployment optimization module has been proposed. The primary purpose of this module is to supervise and coordinate AI/ML-driven automation throughout the entire service lifecycle. Specifically, during service deployment, the optimization engine evaluates incoming network service requests—described through service graphs or descriptors that include functional parameters (e.g., hardware specifications) and non-functional requirements (e.g., end-to-end latency and

availability). Using sophisticated AI/ML models, it partitions these service graphs, decomposes non-functional criteria, and optimally matches functional requirements.

B. Federated learning for Slice and Resource Management

Federated learning (FL) is a crucial enabling technology for managing and orchestrating computing resources related to heterogeneous network slices within the RAN-Edge domain [16], [17]. Specifically, it supports the development of a Service Level Agreement (SLA)-driven adaptive learning rate mechanism. This approach effectively addresses key challenges associated with managing resources in dynamic and resource-constrained telecommunications environments.

In federated learning scenarios, clients typically possess diverse datasets. The adaptive learning rate mechanism mitigates data heterogeneity by dynamically adjusting the learning rate, ensuring efficient and uniform model updates across all participating clients. Telecommunications environments, particularly within the 6G RAN-edge domain, frequently experience varying operational conditions. To maintain performance consistency, the learning rate adapts in real-time based on client performance metrics, enabling the system to respond effectively to environmental fluctuations.

SLAs play a critical role in maintaining performance and reliability standards. Integrating SLA metrics, such as CPU load, into the adaptive learning rate adjustment ensures federated learning processes remain compliant with SLA requirements. This integration allows the adaptive mechanism to consider resource constraints common in telecommunications environments, thus enhancing the overall efficiency of the federated learning process.

By dynamically tuning the learning rate according to SLA metrics, this method significantly improves the convergence speed of the global model compared to traditional static learning rates. Such dynamic adjustments help the system to overcome inherent limitations of fixed learning rates, thereby enhancing responsiveness and resource optimization.

These adaptive solutions are intended to be integrated into AI-driven Management and Orchestration Frameworks [18], [19], facilitating efficient slice and resource orchestration within a closed-loop system. This integration promotes zero-touch automation in resource allocation, especially in edge computing scenarios. CPU load, a vital indicator of resource utilization, serves as one of the supervised outputs. Adjustments to the learning rate informed by SLA metrics further align predictive models with expected resource utilization, ensuring optimal system performance.

C. Dynamic Infrastructure Orchestration

Rapidly increasing data traffic and the growing demand for pervasive connectivity have made the convergence of terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) indispensable. NTNs—encompassing satellite constellations, High-Altitude Platforms (HAPs), and UAVs—expand coverage, reinforce network resilience, and reduce latency in targeted regions. Together with terrestrial systems, they form a “3D Network”, uniting ground, aerial, and space communication infrastructure. Such 3D networks are considered as an integral part of the 6G

ecosystem by expanding coverage, enhancing resilience, and supporting the ultra-low latency demands.

However, the seamless orchestration of this multi-layered environment and the insurance of continuous, high-performance communication are challenging, especially when dealing with mobile infrastructure such as drones, satellites, and HAPs, creating constantly shifting topologies. Traditional network management frameworks, including ETSI NFV for virtualized infrastructure and ETSI MEC for edge computing, must be enhanced with Software-Defined Networking (SDN) principles that address the variability of radio access, transport, and core networks. The chief difficulty arises from the mobility and intermittent connectivity of the aerial components, as their changing positions can undermine reliable communication and service availability. Sophisticated mobility management strategies are therefore essential, requiring real-time tracking and coordination to mitigate disruptions and maintain service continuity.

To handle these issues, a dynamic management approach is introduced in [20], [21] whereby the Virtualized Infrastructure Manager (VIM) coordinates both satellite and terrestrial resources. By leveraging lightweight orchestration tools like K3S for containerized deployments, this system promotes autonomous and scalable management of computing, storage, and network functions, even in hardware-adaptive environments that demand rapid reconfiguration (such as FPGAs). Furthermore, an Infrastructure Mobility Management Model is proposed to unify global and domain-specific mobility functions. At the highest level, a Global Mobility Management Function (GMMF) registers and discovers domains, ensuring efficient resource allocation as physical platforms traverse different regions. Domain Mobility Management Functions (DMMFs) supervise mobility within specific spheres, and Local Mobility Management Functions (LMMFs) provide real-time and predictive updates on the precise location of these platforms.

By integrating terrestrial and non-terrestrial elements under a shared orchestration framework and employing real-time mobility management, service continuity is maintained despite highly dynamic conditions. This cohesive 3D network strategy supports ubiquitous connectivity, enables future-proof communication systems, and ensures efficient, scalable, and resilient service delivery across geographically diverse environments.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper provided an overview of the key enablers necessary to address the challenges of scalability and sustainability in deploying AI-driven, zero-touch Management and Orchestration (MANO) for 6G networks. We identified and categorized three main groups of enablers: high-level service management components, solutions for managing the cloud-to-edge computing continuum, and technologies for resource management in dynamically changing environments. All these enablers will be crucial in ensuring the efficient orchestration and operation of 6G networks.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported financially by the EU in the context of Horizon Europe SNS-JU projects: DESIRE6G (G.A.

No 101096466), ADROIT6G (G.A. No 101095363), HEXA-X-II (G.A. No 101095759), ETHER (G.A. No 101096526), VERGE (G.A. No 101096034) and EU Horizon Europe CL4 project aeROS (G.A. No 101069732).

REFERENCES

- [1] O-RAN Alliance, "69 New or Updated O-RAN Technical Documents Released since November 2023," 22 03 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.o-ran.org/blog/69-new-or-updated-o-ran-technical-documents-released-since-november-2023>.
- [2] ETSI GS ZSM 001, "Zero-touch network and Service Management (ZSM); Requirements based on documented scenarios: ETSI GS ZSM 001 V1.1.1", 2019.
- [3] 3GPP TS 28.812, "Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects; Telecommunication management; Study on scenarios for Intent driven management services for mobile networks (Release 16)", March 2020.
- [4] G. Pongrácz et al., (2023, October). Towards extreme network KPIs with programmability in 6G. In Proceedings of the Twenty-fourth International Symposium on Theory, Algorithmic Foundations, and Protocol Design for Mobile Networks and Mobile Computing (pp. 340-345).
- [5] N. Bartzoudis et al., (2024). Agile FPGA Computing at the 5G Edge: Joint Management of Accelerated and Software Functions for Open Radio Access Technologies. Electronics, 13(4), 701.
- [6] VERGE, "Deliverable D1.3 - "VERGE's final system architecture", 2024.
- [7] E. Rojas et al., "Beyond Multi-Access Edge Computing: Essentials to Realize a Mobile, Constrained Edge," in IEEE Communications Magazine, vol. 62, no. 1, pp. 156-162, January 2024, doi: 10.1109/MCOM.017.2300056.
- [8] R. Vaño et al., Cloud-Native Workload Orchestration at the Edge: A Deployment Review and Future Directions. Sensors 2023, 23, 2215. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23042215>
- [9] European Commission, "Meta-operating Systems for the Next-Generation IoT and Edge Computing"
- [10] aeROS Continuum Ontology, Available: <https://wp4.pages.aeros-project.eu/t4.1/aeros-continuum/>
- [11] 3GPP, "3GPP TS 23.288: Architecture enhancements for 5G System (5GS) to support network data analytics services, v18.5.0," 27 03 2024. [Online].
- [12] M. Ruiz, F. Tabatabaeimehr, and L. Velasco, "Knowledge Management in Optical Networks: Architecture, Methods and Use Cases [Invited]," IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking, 2020.
- [13] S. Barzegar, M. Ruiz, and L. Velasco, "Packet Flow Capacity Autonomous Operation based on Reinforcement Learning," MDPI Sensors, 2021.
- [14] L. Velasco et al., "Autonomous and Energy Efficient Lightpath Operation based on Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing," IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, 2021.
- [15] M. Wooldridge, An introduction to multiagent systems, John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [16] Hexa-x-ii, "Deliverable D6.2 – Foundations on 6G Smart Network Management and Orchestration Enablers," 2023.
- [17] ADROIT6G, "Deliverable D4.1 - AI-driven Management & Orchestration and Control frameworks - Initial", 2024.
- [18] J. Pérez-Valero et al., (2022, December). AI-driven Orchestration for 6G Networking: the Hexa-X vision. In 2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Wkshps) (pp. 1335-1340). IEEE.
- [19] L. Blanco et al., "AI-Driven Framework for Scalable Management of Network Slices," in IEEE Communications Magazine, vol. 61, no. 11, pp. 216-222, November 2023, doi: 10.1109/MCOM.005.2300147.
- [20] K. Ntontin et al., "ETHER: A 6G Architectural Framework for 3D Multi-Layered Networks," 2024 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), Dubai, United Arab Emirates, 2024, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/WCNC57260.2024.10570731.
- [21] ETHER, "Deliverable D2.4 - Final report on ETHER network architecture, interfaces and architecture evaluation", 2024.